

APPLICATION FOR ADMISSION 2023/2024 SESSION NOW OPEN!!!

The Universities in Nigerian are under the oversight of the National Universities Commission (NUC), a parastatal under the Federal Ministry of Education. This body is saddled by law to approve and grant operational license to each proposed university, evaluate and accredit courses offered in each university and regulate the minimum standards in terms of infrastructure and academics.

Besides the above, each University in the country enjoys autonomy in terms of appointments and promotions. The Head of each University is the Vice Chancellor who is responsible for the overall management and academic progress of the university. The University is in turn split into Faculties or Schools (also sometimes called colleges or institutes) and Departments. A faculty is made up of related courses while a department is each course of study. For instance, the Faculty of Social Sciences at the University of Lagos is made up of the departments of Economics, Sociology, Psychology and Political Science. The faculty is headed by a Dean while each department is headed by a Head of Department (HOD).

The principal officers of a university are as follows:

VISITOR: The Visitor is the President in terms of Federal Universities, Governor in the Case of State owned universities and the Chief promoter/proprietor in the case of private universities.

CHANCELLOR The Chancellor

PRO-CHANCELLOR The Pro-Chancellor serves as the Chairman of the University's governing council.

VICE CHANCELLOR The Vice Chancellor is the Chief Executive of the University and is charged with the general responsibility for matters relating to the day-to-day management of the institution.

DEP. VICE CHANCELLOR The Deputy Vice Chancellor serves as the deputy to the Chief Executive and as such carries out other functions as may be assigned to him by the Provost.

REGISTRAR The registrar is the Chief Administrative Officer of the University. He is responsible to the Provost for the day-to-day administration of the institution,

amongst others.

BURSAR The bursar is responsible for the day-to-day administration and control of the financial affairs of the University, amongst others.

LIBRARIAN The Librarian is responsible for the administration of the University Library and the coordination of the library services of the University, among others

ADMINISTRATIVE ORGANS OF THE UNIVERSITIES

GOVERNING COUNCIL

The governing council of a university (sometimes called Board of Governors) oversees the academic, business and student affairs of the University. The governing council by law is charged with the general control (including appointment and promotion of staff) and superintendence of policy, finances and property of the university. In order to do this, it sets up a standing committee called finance and general purposes committee which comprises the following members: chairman of the council, the vice chancellor, one senate member who must also be a member of council, and at least two members of the council who are drawn from the university community. This is a powerful committee of decision making status. It hammers out all budget proposal, discusses all promotions and appointments and conditions of service of university staff before tabling them in council for deliberations and approval.

UNIVERSITY SENATE

The senate is the academic touchstone of each university and is in charge of all matters which deal with academic duties; it controls teaching, research, admission, discipline of students, examination, the organization of halls of residence, and the award of degree (Federal Ministry of Education, 2003).

TUITION FEES

The Federal Universities are non-fee paying institutions and are thus fully funded by the Federal Government. Some of the State Universities attracts some fees are thus subsidized by the respective State Governments. The private Universities are fully

fee payable institutions and have no subsidies as they are pure commercial and private ventures set up by the respective promoters/proprietors.